
THE PROPHETIC CALL TRADITION: AN EXEGETICAL STUDY OF ISAIAH 6: 1-10 IN
AFRICAN CONTEXT

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INTRODUCTION

The Biblical prophets occupy a special place in the history of the Israelites as a nation. Their distinction arises from the role they played in the establishment of God's institution among men. The prophets see themselves as God's mouthpiece and intermediaries between God and man and because of their privilege to receive messages from God they purport to have been called by God. Akao observes that "the prophet's call legitimizes their ministry and also authenticates their message which they claimed is from God" (1993:1).

One of the prophetic books important to most Old Testament scholars is the book of Isaiah. The book is simple and it narrates the call and commission of Isaiah in a unique fashion that is different from the call narratives of other prophets.¹ The call and commission of Isaiah is highlighted in Chapter 6 of the book, which focuses on the Divine call and commission of the prophet. Barton (2003:24) noted that "the written account of the call of Isaiah may have been put together in its present form by the prophet himself. If it is indeed so, the calling of Isaiah forms the pinnacle of his prophecy." Before one proceeds on the exegesis of Isaiah, it suffices to inquire who is Isaiah? From the record available Isaiah was a prophet in Jerusalem between 750-700 B.C. The name Isaiah is derived from the Hebrew word *yeshayahu* meaning Yahweh saves or Yahweh is salvation Hanke (1997:222). Isaiah is the first of the major prophet in the English Bible and the first of the latter prophets in the Hebrew Canon Ridderbos (1992: 521). Both Jewish and Christian traditions accepted Isaiah as the author of the book that bears his name. It is interesting to note that the name Isaiah appears sixteen times in the body of the book. Jesus referred to Isaiah at least four times as the author of the book. Schmidt remarks that it is clear that Isaiah's ministry was concerned primarily with Judah and Jerusalem at a very critical period of the nation's history 739-700 B.C and that it formed the background for his prophecies (1996: 217). Gottwald (1962:311) observes that several of his most significant messages are directly related to the critical situation around Judea at this period in time such as the Syro-Ephraimitic war in 734 B.C and the Sennecherib crisis of 701. Isaiah was well known in Jerusalem as a priest and prophet and most of the rulers at this period knew him. Clement (1980:305) remarks that Isaiah was a noble man with high education and concludes that

"The ease of royal contact may have been due to a blood relationship Isaiah held to the royal line. Jewish tradition says that Isaiah's father Amoz was a brother of King Amaziah, the Father of Uzziah, thus making Isaiah a cousin of the King Uzziah"

There are different opinions as to whether Isaiah had received his call before this time or not. Different biblical scholars and commentators have offered series of useful suggestions on the call narratives of Isaiah within the context of the book. When compared his call narratives with other call narratives like Ezekiel and Jeremiahs, the call narratives of Isaiah is contrary to the general call narratives of the prophets like Ezekiel and Jeremiah whose call falls within the first chapter of the book (Akao 1993: 68). Though the desire of Isaiah to preach stem from the beginning of the book where some scholars see Isaiah as a teacher of the law and not a prophet, his prophetic ministry started from Chapter 6 (House). This chapter is seeing as the call narratives of Isaiah which the writer wants to explore. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is three folds; one is to explore the call of Isaiah in its context and two, to exegete the call narrative text and three, to apply the text to the contemporary church in Africa.

Isaiah is a prophet per excellence. He operated as a prophet to the nation. He lived in the royal court and was referred to as a royal court prophet. Wood (2003:503) suggests many attributes to him which can be described below

1. Isaiah was a prince of prophet
2. He was one of the intellectuals of his days

3. He was a prophet of outstanding courage
4. He exhibited love for the royal court
5. He exhibited spiritual maturity in dealing with the king.

2. The Literary Genre of the Book of Isaiah 1-6

Most Scholars see the book of Isaiah as the gate way to the prophetic writings. They see the book as the beginning of the prophetic segment of the Hebrew canon. As the opening prophecy, it sets the tone for the rest of the books. Themes, images, and personae that appear here emerge again and again in Isaiah, Jeremiah and Ezekiel. The importance of this observation lies in its ability to help explain the logic of the placement of Isaiah Chapter 6 Clement (1977:45).

The prophetic genre uses both narrative and poetryⁱⁱ to proclaim its message.ⁱⁱⁱ Thus, what separates prophecy from the law and the writings is its content, not its mode of composition. B. D. Napier argues that five basic themes distinguish prophetic literature: These are (1) Word and symbol, (2) election and covenant, (3) rebellion and judgment, (4) compassion and redemption, and (5) consummation (1982:254). R. Clements basically agrees with Napier. He thinks canonical Hebrew writing stresses the inspiration of the prophet's words and the destruction and restoration of Israel. Clements says "special emphasis was attached" to restoration and that Israel's eventual renewal assumes a variety of forms in the prophets. Napier and Clement offer a balanced view of prophetic themes, in contrast to commentators who tend to over-emphasize the prophets' concern with sin and doom. Isaiah 1-6 constantly claims to present God's own words. Twice the passage says that Isaiah received these messages as "visions" from the Lord (1:1; 2:1). God is quoted repeatedly (1:2-3, 24-6; 5:1-2; etc).

Chapter 6 presents an episode where Isaiah speaks with God face to face. The claims for direct inspiration permeate these chapters and the whole prophecy as well. Yahweh and the prophet denounce sin in great detail in chapters 1-6. These denunciations of sins set the stage for later calls to repentance and offers of forgiveness and reconciliation. Often, the Lord announces the nation's wickedness, for example in Isaiah 1:2-3, 18-23, and then Isaiah explains the implications of Yahweh's comment for Israel in Isaiah 1:4-9 (Watts 1985:77). At other times, the prophet introduces God's condemnations in Isaiah 3:13-15. Israel's wickedness becomes so numerous and evident by the end of chapter 5, that Isaiah had to pronounce woe on the inhabitant of Israel who did evil.

In Isaiah 6:5, the prophet identified himself with the sins of the nation and said "I am a man of unclean lips, and I live among a people of unclean lips." Because of this sin, Yahweh will punish Israel and Yahweh will purge the rebellious nation of its atrocities. This purging will occur on the day of Yahweh, a day of vengeance, a day in which Yahweh will humble the proud among the leaders of Israel (2: 12-19 3:1-12) and general populace (3:15-4:1). Destruction and Exile would be the most obvious sign that the "day" has come (5:13-14). Only a remnant of righteous persons will remain in the land after the judgment ceases (6:9-13). God's method of redeeming his people is to first punish them and later on effect their deliverance. After the devastation, all nations shall stream in to Jerusalem to worship Yahweh. Hear what Isaiah says:

“The word that Isaiah the son of Amoz saw concerning Judah and Jerusalem. And it shall come to pass in the last days, that the mountain of the Lord's house shall be established in the top of the mountains, and shall be exalted above the hills; and all nations shall flow into it. And many people shall go and say come ye and let us go up to mountain of the Lord, to the house of the God of Jacob: and he will teach us of his ways and we will walk in his paths: for out of Zion shall go forth the law, and the word of the Lord from Jerusalem...” (2:1-3 KJV).

The filth of the daughter of Zion will be washed away, and the "survivors in Israel" will enjoy God's protection in Zion (4:2-6). A remnant of people will survive even the harshest punishment (6:13). Though chapters 1-6 stress sin and judgment, they do not neglect restoration altogether. Renewal remains Yahweh's ultimate purpose. Clearly, Isaiah 1-6 introduces the basic themes of the prophetic genre. Isaiah will participate in the main traditions of prophetic preaching. Since condemnation and calls for repentance are so prominent, his audience may not appreciate his message. His ministry may not prove easy or popular.

3. Historical Background of Isaiah Chapter 1-6

Some scholars attempt to date chapters 1-5 fairly specifically. For instance, Hayes and Irvine note that Isaiah 7's setting is 733B. C, since it describes the Syro-Ephraimite war. At this time Syria and Samaria invade Judah (7:1-2), which causes Ahaz to ask Assyria for help (2 Kings 16:7-9). Since chapter 6 is dated about seven years

earlier, Hayes and Irvine suggest that most, if not all, of chapters 1-6 is preached between 745-740 B C, or, in other words, a few years before Uzziah's death. In their scheme, Isaiah 1-6 comes from Isaiah's early ministry, when Judah's wickedness has yet to place them in political danger. Chapters 7-12, then, are sermons delivered during and after the 733 B. C.'s crisis that inaugurates a new, politically conscious phase of Isaiah's ministry (Hayes and Irvine 1987: 23).

Other commentators are more cautious. For instance, J. Oswalt (1986:173) thinks chapters 1-5 are broad introductory messages that have no "direct relationship with chaps. 7-12 than they do with any other segment of the book." Thus, they can only be dated sometime during Isaiah's career. R. Clements says that chapter 1 is an introductory collection of texts from various periods of Isaiah's ministry. Most of chapters 2-6 originate during 733-725 B C, since these passages are similar in content to Isaiah 7-9, though messages of hope like 2:1-5, 4:2-6, and 6:12-13 are post-exilic additions (Clement 1980:173). E. J. Young essentially agrees with Oswalt's assessment of the section, and though they date more oracles after 587 B. C than Clements, Kaiser and Gray noted that chapters 1-6 come from eighth-century Isaiah. Other authors could be cited, but the point has been made. These writers conclude that Isaiah 1-6 arises from a variety of eighth-century settings and introduces the book in some way. All agree that Isaiah 6 occurs by 740.

The prophecy itself offers no exact life setting for chapters 1-5. Two inscriptions appear, but they merely state that Isaiah delivers these messages sometime "during the reigns of Uzziah, Jotham, Ahaz, and Hezekiah" (1:1) and that they consist of comments "concerning Judah and Jerusalem" (2:1). Chapter 6 originates "in the year of King Uzziah's death" (6:1), but this reference reveals little. It sets a date for the call experience without divulging how Uzziah's death affects Isaiah. Young observes that the book's internal evidence can be interpreted in a number of ways, as the survey of scholarly opinions noted above indicates. Therefore, chapters 1-5 can only be dated sometime during the reigns of the kings listed in 1:1, or between 783-687 (233). Isaiah chapter 6 occurs by 740. Isaiah's ministry spans from this period and concludes no sooner than 701, when Sennacherib invades Judah (cf. Isaiah 36-37) (Irvine 1987:131-132).

Because chapter 6 mentions Uzziah's death, it is possible to suggest a general historical situation for Isaiah 1-6. Uzziah rules effectively from 783-742 B. C (NCBC 2-8). He helps Judah attain economic and military success at a time when Jeroboam II (786-746 B. C) enjoys an even greater reign in Samaria. Despite these prosperous times, Yahweh is not pleased with the people. Hosea and Amos, who minister during the earlier decades of Uzziah and Jeroboam's era, charge the people and their rulers with a variety of individual and societal sins. By the time Uzziah dies, the people are ripe for judgment. Assyria will soon threaten the region and will eventually destroy Samaria. As a new prophet, Isaiah should have even less hope for Israel's immediate future than his predecessors (Bright 1972: 288-308). Irvine notes that:

Isaiah Chapter 6 is an autobiography account of a vision which Isaiah experienced in 734-733 the death year of Uzziah while the vision dates to the time of the Syro-Ephraimitic war, the text does not reflect directly on the events of the war, it is significant for our purposes only in so far as it may attest generally to the different attitudes of Isaiah towards the Judeans (1990: 132)

4. Rhetorical Structural Analysis of Isaiah Chapters 1-6

The rhetorical structure of the book of Isaiah is united in its themes and subject as the writer sees it. The images and characters portrayed in the book points to the fact that Isaiah actually holds its pieces together. House citing E. V. Roberts says:

The Structure is a matter of the relationship among parts that are usually described in terms of cause and effect, position in time, association, symmetry, and balance and proportion. . . . Literary artists universally aim at a unified impression in their works, and because literature is a time art . . . , the study of structure attempts to demonstrate that the idea and the resulting arrangements of parts produce a total impression. (House)

Because of the uncertainty of the historical background of the book of Isaiah, this section's structure is particularly important to grasp. Ridderbos (1992: 521) posits that there are certain parallelism that exists in these chapters. First, both chapters 1 and 2 have inscriptions which separate them into two distinct segments.

Condemnation of a merely external form of worship (1:1-31) and prophecy relating to the coming kingdom of peace (2:2-5:30), Second, chapters 2-4 form a unit, since (2:1-4) describes Israel's glorious future, (2:5-4:1) warns of coming judgment, and (4:2-6) returns to the day of Yahweh this will usher in the restoration of the people of God and bring down judgment on the proud and exalted. The haughty women of Zion will be dealt with and those who have forgotten Yahweh will regret forever.

Third, Isaiah 5:1- 7 is a song of the vineyard. It is a parable song that talks about Israel's unrepentant rebellion against Yahweh. Fourth, chapters 5:8-30 consists of woes against Israel. Fifth, Isaiah 6:1-13 consists of Isaiah's inaugural vision. The following chapter of Isaiah 7:1 presents a totally different setting from Isaiah chapter 6. Except for Isaiah 5:1- 7 and Isaiah 5:8-30, each "stitch" also marks a thematic transition (Ridderbos 521).

L. Liebreich (1954:38) notes that there are variations on the word ("hear") and ("holy") which occurs throughout the chapters. Israel is told to "hear" or "obey" in both 1:2 and 1:10 (36-37). The Torah is the object of the "hearing" in 1:10, and 5:24 blames rejection of the Torah for Israel's certain punishment. Further, 1:4 and 5:24 charge that Israel has "rejected the holy one of Israel," 5:16, 19, and 24 mention Yahweh's holiness, and chapter 6 presents Yahweh as the thrice-holy one.

Douglas R. Jones (1964:468) noted that the thematic progression is evident in chapter one which utilizes several common prophetic rhetorical devices, each intended to shame the people into repentance. He observes that Yahweh exposes Israel's rebelliousness by comparing them unfavorably to an ox and an ass (Isaiah 1:2-3), and God rhetorically asks the question; why are they determined to perish? (Isaiah 1:4-9), the land has been devastated, so why do they remain stubborn? Why not "wash" themselves of this sin (Isaiah 1:10-17)? After all, repentance will bring blessings (Isaiah 1:18-20). As a last resort, Isaiah calls Israel a harlot (Isaiah 1:21-26) and once again demands repentance (Isaiah 1:27-31).

Chapter 2 of Isaiah uses a new paradigm to begin this rhetoric section. "It shall come to pass" this statement is distinct and unique and distinguishes it from chapter 1, but it themes of sin and punishment continues with the restoration sequence. House citing P. R. Ackroyd places 2:1-5 with chapter 1, thus creating two segments that begin with condemnation and conclude with hope (1:2-2:5 and 2:6-4:6).

This rhetorical strategy according to House allows Israel to receive the prophet's message however they wish, either as a message of doom or hope (House 1990: 211). Unfortunately, the Israelites reject threats from Yahweh and also not minding the promises from Yahweh. Isaiah was despaired over the nation's immorality and rebellious attitudes towards Yahweh's instruction. He identified himself with the sin of his people and said

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"Woe is me for I am a man of unclean lips and I lived among the unclean people" (Isaiah 6:5). Despite the promises and the vision of a glorious future for Israel the people rejected God's message therefore, Yahweh declares Israel a hopelessly proud and idolatrous people (2:6-11). God will therefore set a "day of judgment for Israel, a day of reckoning" (2:12) a day to deal with all idols and punish the proud, rich and haughty officials and citizens (2:12-22; 2:1-15).

In summary, there is a rhetorical linkage from chapter one to chapter five which describes the sinful condition of the nation of Israel. Young noted that the first five chapters have done more than introduce the book's contents or simply stress the message over the messenger (54). Chapter 5 begins with a parable (5:1-7), moves to a series of woes (5:8-23), and ends with predictions of exile (5:24-30). The parable, or "song" (5:1), denounces the way Israel has destroyed itself through oppression and murder (5:7). Since Israel rejects God, only "woe" can result. "Woe" awaits all who devastate the land (5:8), live for wine (5:9), pervert God's word (5:20), and take bribes and corrupt themselves with women (5:23). And since these people refuse Yahweh's blessings then what remains for them is disaster (2:1-5; 4:2-6; 5:1-2), Yahweh will visit them with Judgment, a purging disaster was inevitable (5:24-30) (Oswalt1986:173).

The dimension that chapter 6 brought into the scene is widely debated among scholars. The genre of Isaiah chapter 6 has provoked arguments among scholars from various persuasions. Some scholars see chapter 6 as a concluding part of chapter five and an introduction to the chapter that follows. House remarks that:

“Some of the debate stems from curiosity about a call story so late in a prophecy, while concern about chronology fuels other discussions. Scholars normally accept variations on two basic solutions. Either this chapter discusses Isaiah's initial call, and the function of chapters 1-5 must be considered as an introductory word of some kind, or chapter 6 begins a second phase of the prophet's work.”(1992:210)

Most commentators adopt the first solution. E. J. Young and G. Grogan simply believe Isaiah stresses his message more than himself. This theory does not explain why Isaiah would ever insert himself into the story, or why more of the major elements of Isaiah's message are not included in chapters 1-5. House citing K. Budde's *Eine emeinverstandliche Auslegung der Denkschrift des Propheten* contended that chapter 6:1-8:18 forms "a memoir written by the prophet himself, and relating to prophecies at the time of the Syro-Ephraimite war." He therefore, submits that redactional concerns account for the call story coming after other material. Chapters 1-5 and 6:1-8:18 may have existed as separate collections before being joined by a final editor (<http://www.faculty.gordon.edu> 2007).

Though this redactional reconstruction deserves extensive discussion, it is impossible to do so here. It is only possible to note the function of chapters 1-5 and chapter 6 in this viewpoint. Clements states that the main "theme of this memoir is how Ahaz came to refuse the message which Isaiah gave to him" and how this refusal brought punishment on king and people. Similarly, Kaiser concludes that the call account reveals "that God's judgment was already decreed when he called him to a task that went beyond all normal feeling and understanding." (Kaiser 1972:73). Both Kaiser and Clements highlight refusal and judgment. To them, chapters 1-5 announce these themes, chapter 6 calls Isaiah to proclaim them, and chapters 7-12 show the prophet experiencing them. From all these speculations there is no textual evidence to back up their claims. The writer agrees with the position of Barry Webb that Chapter 6 of Isaiah stand centrally within chapters 1-12 and is intimately related to both what precedes and what follows in order words it serves as both "a suitable conclusion to the chapters before it, and an equally suitable introduction to the chapters which follow (1996:58). Isaiah Chapter 6 does act as a linking text. Chapters 1-5 detail the sins of Israel and how those sins postpone God's blessings for the nation.

Clearly the nation ought to repent, yet refuses to do so. Chapter 6 admits this national sin and announces its long-term cure. Chapters 7-12 explain how Isaiah announces the cure to the rebellious people but have little success in changing them. Thus, the reader learns Israel is a difficult audience, Isaiah has a difficult task, and Isaiah will experience a difficult ministry. Call to Office (Payne 1992: 724).

Watts suggested that Chapter six has unity and movement and it is composed of five parts these are:

1. vs. 1-4 the hall of the Lord, Heavenly King
2. vs. 5-7 the purging of Isaiah's sin
3. vs. 8-10 the task for the people
4. vs. 11 how long will the prophesying about suffering last
5. vs.12-13 if some survive and return what of them (Watts 1985:70).

While Hayes and Irvine, adopts the following combinations

1. Isaiah's Vision of God (6:1-4);
2. Isaiah's Sin and its Cleansing (6:5-7);
3. Isaiah's Commission (6:8-10);
4. Isaiah's Difficult Ministry and Israel's Difficult Future (6:11-13) (Hayes and Irvine 1987: 110). Watt's analysis of chapter 6 shows that vs. 8-10 does not agree with the translation which clearly stated the task before Isaiah (Watts 1985: 70). The writer agrees with Hayes and Irvin analysis of the chapter that reveals Isaiah's commission.

5a. Translation of Isaiah 6:1-8

1. In the year that King Uzziah died I saw the Lord sitting and exalted on the throne and his robe fill the temple
2. Seraphim stood above him with each one having six wings; with two he covered his face, with two he covered his feet and with two he flew
3. And he called to one another and said Holy, Holy, Holy, is the Lord of Host for the whole earth is full of his glory.
4. The cubit of the threshold began to shake at the voice of one who is calling and the house was filled with

smoke

5. And I said woe to me for I am ruined for I am a man with unclean lips and I dwelt among unclean people for my eyes have seen the king the Lord of Hosts

6. Then one of the seraphs flew over to me with a live coal, which he had taken from the altar with a pair of tongs

7. He touched it to my lips and declared, "Now that this has touched your lips, your guilt shall depart And your sin be purged away.

8. Then I heard the voice of my Lord saying, "Whom shall I send? Who will go for us?" And I said, "Here am I; send me."

5b. Prophetic Call of Isaiah: Exegesis of Isaiah 6:1-10

David F. Payne correctly identifies Isaiah chapter 6 as the Prophet's Call to Office (Payne 724) while N. Habel refers to it as Isaiah's call story (Habel 1985:310ff). The chapter is quite unique in content because it's describing the prophet's encounter with Yahweh. The writer sees this experience of Isaiah as an encounter with God that serves as a foundation for his call and commission to ministry. This experience resembles that of Jeremiah and Ezekiel and it is like the tradition of the call of the prophet in the Old Testament the difference between them is that Jeremiah had been called before he started preaching, the same with Ezekiel but Isaiah had been preaching several years before he was divinely called. Akao observes that the prophetic call tradition seems to be based on a setting of messenger-overlord relationship (4).^{iv} The call of Isaiah is parallel to other call stories like those of Gideon, Moses, Jeremiah, and Ezekiel. Each account includes the manifestation of the presence of Yahweh, a voice from Yahweh, a commission, and a comment about the difficulty of the task and an assurance of support from Yahweh (Smith 1924:181). These elements, along with Isaiah's sense of sinfulness, provide the four main thematic divisions of this chapter (House).

1. Isaiah 6:1-4: Isaiah saw God's Glory
2. Isaiah 6:5-7: Isaiah saw His Sinfulness
3. Isaiah 6:8-10: Isaiah receives God's Call and Commissioning

1. Isaiah 6:1-4: Isaiah saw God's Glory

In verse 1 of Isaiah chapter 6, the prophet records that "in the year that king Uzziah died I saw the Lord." King Uzziah was one of the powerful kings in Israel. His reign witnessed tremendous growth and expansion. He had an organized army and well articulated political and economic structure. During his reign, the nation of Israel witnessed geographical expansion and economic prosperity. He was a good king but towards the end of his reign he committed blunders. He entered the temple and burn incense to the Lord which was the duty of the priest and was punished for his action (2 Chronicles 26:21:1ff).

The date of Uzziah's death was difficult to ascertain however, Hayes and Irvine observe that the date scholars assigned the kings of Isaiah's era "may vary as much as a decade or more"(Hayes and Irvine Isaiah 34). Uzziah's reign is particularly hard to fix, since he is co-regent with his son Jotham in the last years of his life. The date speculated for Uzziah's death was between 742-740 BC, though, leaves enough time for the events of Jotham, Ahaz, and Hezekiah's reigns (Bright 1972: 54).

Many scholars argue that Uzziah's death greatly affected Isaiah. For example, Jester William thinks this king, who had led Israel so effectively, was probably the young prophet's hero (Williams 58). Oswalt notes that Uzziah was the only king Isaiah had known. Thus, his death, and the mounting Assyrian threat brought on by Tiglath-Pileser III's ascendancy, helped Isaiah realize that Israel was at a crossroads (Oswalt 1986: 177). Ultimate spiritual and political decisions would soon be made (Smith 58). Smith's theory is fascinating, but no textual evidence to support his claim. House concluded that early readers of Isaiah would definitely recognize the transitional nature of this time (NIBC 1992: 58).

aF_nIw> ~r'ä aSePKi-l[; bveÿO yn"±doa]-ta, Isaiah said I saw *Yahweh Adonai* sitting on a throne, high and

lifted up and his glory filled the temple. This phrase means that *Yahweh* is highly exalted supreme and ruler of the universe. This statement signifies that Yahweh is in total control of the affairs in Judah. *Yahweh* is in control of the political and economic situation of the nation. Though king Uzziah as good and brilliant as he was may be dead but the Lord remains sovereign forever. A second phrase says "his robe fill the temple" this phrase

reinforces the picture of God's greatness. God's glory is too magnificent for the temple to contain. Franz Delitsch submits that

The heavenly temple is the super-terrestrial place which Yahweh, by manifesting Himself there to the angels and the blessed, makes into heaven and temple. While he shows his glory there, He must at the same time conceal it, because the creature cannot bear it. Isaiah sees the Lord, and what he sees besides is the state robe of the indescribable One, which fills the whole space. There is therefore no room for standing: and this fixes the manner in which the seraphim are seen (145).

Isaiah 6. 2. The Word "Seraphim," or "burning ones," is used variously in the Old Testament. This term is used to describe a fiery serpent (Num 21:6) or flying serpent (Isaiah 14:29; 30:6) (BDB 1979:977). The seraphim are heavenly beings that serve in the presence of God. Here they covered God with their wings and fly around to give praises to God.

6.3. The Seraphim cried one to another affirming the Holiness of God. They declared the holiness of God in unison. They are six winged creature pairing in twos and echoing the word $tAa+b'c. hw''\grave{a}hy > vAd\beta q' vAd\pm q' \check{Y}vAd\acute{o}q'$ qados qados, qados is Yahweh of host (BDB 977) There is no reason to attach any formula to these sayings. The number three employed here is primarily for the sake of emphasis. God is infinite and totally different in nature from all created beings. The second phrase $\`Ad*AbK. \#r,a'Ph'-lk' al\{im$ "The whole earth is full of his glory" signifies that just as the glory of God fill the temple in the same way his glory fill the earth. The Lord by His nature governs and judges the earth by his holiness. Oswalt rightly remarks "this verse sounds wonderful until one realizes that "where God's glory is manifested, there is judgment for sin, for the two cannot exist side by side. Yahweh's ethical perfection ("holy") makes his presence eliminate sin" (Oswalt 1986: 181)

6.4. The post of the doors were shaking by the voice of the Seraphim and the house was filled with smoke. The reference to smoke here re-emphasizes God's presence. Smoke is like cloud (2 Chronicle 5:13) which symbolizes the presence of God. In Exodus, the cloud in smoke form usually accompanies the appearances of God (Exodus 23:18ff; Exodus 40:34 and 1 Kings 8:10ff). The smoke protects Isaiah from viewing the Lord, which could cause Isaiah's death, for no one can see the Lord and live. Engnell says regardless of the smoke's exact purpose, Isaiah has now seen evidence of Yahweh's greatness, heard the seraphim's comments on God's holiness, and felt the shaking of the building. His senses have been assaulted by Yahweh's power (Engnell 37)

2. Isaiah 6:5-7: Isaiah saw His Sinfulness and was Cleansed

Vs. 6:5. Given his experience in 6:1-4, it is no wonder Isaiah cries, "Woe is me, for I am ruined." This "woe" yAa is the cry of rejection, a cry of sorrow, Isaiah counted himself as dead because he found himself in the immediate presence of God Light (2001: 29). Why does Isaiah feel so unworthy? Because he knows he is "a man of unclean lips" who lives in a nation filled with unclean lips. "Unclean" often refers to ceremonial uncleanness in the OT, so perhaps Isaiah feels unworthy to remain in God's temple. Delitsch (1921:151) suggests that "this unholiness he names uncleanness of lips is liken to ceremonial uncleanness before Yahweh, Isaiah sees himself among the Seraphim the heavenly being praising the Lord with pure lips. Isaiah mentions his lips because he could not match the praise of the seraphim." Light suggests that lip is a poetic device in which the part stands for the whole, where Isaiah knows that he is wholly unclean (2001:29). Clements offers a better solution. He claims Isaiah realizes his unfitnes to act as God's spokesman. Thus, Isaiah's unclean lips make it an unlikely prophet, just as Israel's unclean lips" make it a poor elect nation. Both Isaiah and the nation should expect "woe" for their "uncleanness" (Clement 1980:75). Not only is he a sinner, but he has also seen God. Jacob has a similar fear, so also Moses (Gen 32:30; Exodus 33:20). Clearly Isaiah has good reason to feel "ruined"(Isaiah 6:6-7). The Seraphim immediately come to Isaiah's aid. They purify his lips with a coal from the divine altar. God's desire to cleanse and forgive is evident. Isaiah can now speak for God. Besides Yahweh's kindness, this cleansing emphasizes the stupidity of Israel's continued rebellion. Forgiveness would come just as quickly for Israel as for Isaiah if the nation would change (1980:75).

3. Isaiah 6:8-10: Isaiah receives God's Call and Commissioning.

6:8. Isaiah heard the Lord saying "Whom shall I send, and who will go for us?" The Lord calls for a messenger who will willingly offer himself for service and Isaiah freely makes a decision, Lord, Here am I Send Me, Watts observes that this is unique to call narratives, but is normal in heavenly throne descriptions Isaiah finds himself, like Moses Ex. 3:10-11 and Jeremiah 1:4-8, faced with the task of being a prophet (Watts 1985:75). The phrase "for us" probably refers to the heavenly council, which is probably the best interpretation regardless of the

identity of "us," Isaiah feels compelled to answer the question that he must tell the people, "Listen and listen, but do not understand. Look and look, but never perceive" (6:9).

Aaàr' Waiër>W WnybiêT'-la;w> '[:Am'v' W[Üm.vi hZ<+h; ~['äl' T'Pr>m;a'w> %lEi rm,aYO`w: `W[d'(Te-la;w>

Then 6:10 uses three hiphil imperatives--"make fat" (dBePk.h;), "make heavy" (!mev.h;)))))

(

wyn"÷y[eb. ha,'r>yI-!P, [v;_h' wyn"ây[ew> dBePk.h; wyn"iz>a'w> hZ<ëh; ~['äh'-ble 'lmev.h;
 `Al* ap'rîw> bv'Pw" !ybi²y" Abðb'l.W [m^av.yI wyn"áz>a'b.W

and "shut" ([v;_h')--to describe the effect of Isaiah's message on the people's heart, ears, and eyes. Since the hiphil carries causative force, it appears that Isaiah must intend to harden the people (House) House citing C. A. Evans notes that the Dead Sea Scrolls change the negative particle -la; ('al) in 6:9 which would mean Isaiah must preach to effect understanding and knowledge. Further, the first Hiphil imperative has no n, which changes the word's meaning to "make appalled." In this reading Israel's appalled heart saves them from horrible sights and sounds (House). He further observes that the LXX makes the verses descriptive, not imperatival. Evans submits that "both the Qumran and Greek texts shift the blame for Israel's sin "from Yahweh and his prophet to the people themselves. He notes that "Four factors argue in favor of the MTs reading of Isaiah's task.

First, changing the first Hiphil imperative does not totally blunt the next two. Why would an appalled heart cause heavy ears and closed eyes?

Second, the latter half of 6:10 begins with a strong averting conjunction "lest." The second half of the verse explains what the first half seeks to avoid, and as Evans suggests, the nuance does not erase this syntactical intention.

Third, Isaiah chaps. 1-5 have already established Israel's callous nature. Further preaching will make them even more callous.

Fourth, Isaiah's startled reaction in 6:11 implies the extreme difficulty of the preaching, not just disappointment at a lack of response. Therefore, Isaiah must live with the fact that he will preach repentance, but that this preaching will harden his hearers (House).

Application of Isaiah's Call in African Context

The need re-evaluate the meaning of worship in this age has become necessary by the fact that in every direction you turn to from the North to the West. South to the East one is confronted with thousands of worship houses. Myriads of people trooping in to this places of worship in their colorful regalia, beautiful headgears and assorted necklaces to pray and worship God, yet the rate of crime and wickedness in our society is yet to be abated. It grows daily. The gap between religious beliefs and character formation has widened drastically so much that hardly can one differentiate between a Christian and non- Christian. Imasogie in one of his homily noted:

That the discrepancy between religious beliefs and daily living has widened tragically not only in Nigeria but all over the world. For instance, in a reported research carried out in the USA, It was discovered that 94% of the 95% American who claimed to belong to one religious group or another also admitted that their religious beliefs have no significance bearing on their business and social life. It sounds shocking and scandalous to hear that there is no perceptible relationship between the people's business and social lives and their religious beliefs and commitments (*God's Message as Such a Time as These* 1993:55).

Isaiah experienced true worship in the temple. He saw God sitting on the throne, high and lifted and his robe fills the whole house. Isaiah saw God in His Glory which drastically changed his perception to life. God is sovereign and he rules in the affairs of men. No matter what mankind is going through God is still God and He is in charge of the affairs of the whole universe. The earthly king may be dead, there may be crisis or confusion in the land yet above all the tragedy of life God still remains on the throne and His power never diminished. What Isaiah saw changed his life and ministry. The church today must seek for genuine worship of God as John

4:23 says those who worship God must do so in Spirit and in truth.

God's vision always brings a true reflection of our person before God.

As Isaiah came face to face with the Holy God he began to realize his sinfulness and short coming. When a man is confronted by God's holiness the result is always that one becomes conscious of his sinfulness and the need for repentance, confession and divine forgiveness becomes imperative. God's Holiness cannot be compromise. God is Holy and he demands holiness and purity from those who worship him. Isaiah saw God's Holiness and cried Woe is me for I am ruined and I lived in the midst of the unclean people. God assured Isaiah of his forgiveness.

Lastly, the need to re-examine one's calling as ministers of the Gospel has become imperative by the fact that everyone now claims to be called of God. Most Bible Colleges and seminaries are full of people who claimed to be called in to God's ministry but are this people truthful to themselves? Are there no underlying motives behind this call? Is it not because of the bad economy and unemployment situation in the nation that drives a lot of people to the seminary? We need to re-examine our call and be sure of God's calling. If God has called definitively he will make provision for it. When God called Isaiah he gave him assurance of his continued abiding presence.

The call of God is irrevocable; every one called in the Bible followed the same pattern, they saw the vision of Yahweh and heard his definite call for an assignment. God will not use an unclean vessel to carry out His assignment in the world. God wants to make use of a cleansed vessel. It was after Isaiah had been cleansed that God called and commission him. It is unfortunate today that some pastors are still sleeping with women in their parishes; while some are peddlers of God's word. It is quite unfortunate that those who bear the vessel of the Lord are unholy and ungodly. Isaiah makes full proof of his ministry and he left his footprint on the sand of time. Ministers of God's word must rise up to their calling and face its challenges. There is no short cut to purity. Finally, be courageous and confident to willingly serve God without fear. He who has called you is faithful; he will not let you down.

NOTES

ⁱ When compares the call of Isaiah with other prophets like Ezekiel, Jeremiah and Amos one discovers that Isaiah's call was unique in the sense that he has been preaching before his actual commission. Chapters 1-5 narrated his preaching among the Israelites while chapter 6 is the beginning point of his commissioning as a prophet to the nation. He saw God and was given a definite assignment to accomplish.

ⁱⁱ The nature and the existence of Hebrew poetry is currently being discussed by scholars. This article uses the terms in their traditional sense. However one defines Hebrew poetry, it is evident that Isaiah 1-5 and Isaiah 36-39 utilize different syntactical styles and that Isaiah 6 combines both styles. Cf. Robert Lowth, *Lectures on the Sacred Poetry of the Hebrews* (original 1753; reprinted Andover: Codman Press, 1829); James Kugel, *The Idea of Biblical Poetry* (New Haven: Yale Publishing Company, 1981); Robert Alter, *The Art of Biblical Poetry* (New York: Basic Books, 1985); and Mona West, "Looking for the Poem: Reflections on the Current and Future Status of Biblical Hebrew Poetry Analysis," *Beyond Form Criticism: Essays in Old Testament Literary Criticism* ed. Paul R. House; (Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 1992).

ⁱⁱⁱ Many early critical scholars tend to argue that the prophets preached judgment, and that any mention of hope must be an addition to the text. Cf. Ivan Engnell's survey and refutation of this tendency in *The Call of Isaiah: An Exegetical and Comparative Study* (Uppsala/Leipzig: A-B. Lundequistska/Otto Harrassowitz, 1949) 20-23.

^{iv} Akao observes that the prophet looks and sees Yahweh in his exalted position or as in the case of Micaiah who saw Yahweh sitting on a throne with the heavenly council in attendance (I king 22:19) and then a voice comes from Yahweh and the prophet is now ready to declare the message of Yahweh to the people even though the prophet may complain of the people's rejection of the message and Yahweh assures the prophet of his protection See Akao, J. O. "Biblical Call Narratives: An Investigation into the Underlying Structure" *Ogbomosho Journal of Theology* 8 (1993): 4

REFERENCES

- Akao, J. O "Biblical Call Narratives: An Investigation to its Underlying Structure" *Ogbomoshu Journal of Theology*, No 8 December 1993
- Albertz, R. A. *History of Israelite Religion in the Old Testament*. Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster John Knox Press, 1994
- Alter, Robert. *The Art of Biblical Poetry* (New York: Basic Books, 1985).
- Anderson, B. W. *The Living World of the Old Testament*. London: The Pitman Press, 1980.
- Barton, J. *Isaiah 1-39*. London: T and T Clark International Print, 2003.
- Bright, John. *A History of Israel* 2nd ed.; Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1972.
- Brown, Francis S, R Drivers and C. Briggs *A Hebrew and English Lexicon of the Old Testament* Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1979.
- Calvin, John. *Commentary of the Book of the Prophet Isaiah, Chapters 1-32* transl. William Pringle: reprinted Grand Rapids, Michigan: Baker Books 1989.
- Clement, R. E. "Isaiah 1-39" *New Century Bible Commentary*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Williams Eerdmans Publishing Press, 1980
- , "Patterns in the Prophetic Canon," *Canon and Authority: Essays in Old Testament Religion and Theology* ed. G. W. Coats and B. Long; Philadelphia: Fortress, 1977.
- Delitzsch, Franz. *Biblical Commentary on the Prophecy of Isaiah* Ed. Rev James Denney in two Vols. New York: Fung and Wagnalis, 1921.
- , *Isaiah* (reprinted) Grand Rapids, Michigan: William Eerdmans, 1980.
- Douglas R. Jones. "Exposition of Isaiah Chapter One Verses One to Nine," *SJT* 17 (1964) 468.
- Engnell, Ivan. *The Call of Isaiah: An Exegetical and Comparative Study* Uppsala/Leipzig: A-B. Lundequistska/Otto Harrassowitz, 1949.
- Gottwald, N. K. *All the Kingdom of the Earth: Israelites in Prophecy and International Relations in the Ancient Near East*. New York: Harper and Row, 1964.
- Gray, G. B. *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Book of Isaiah 1-27* International Critical Commentary. Edinburgh: T and T Clark, 1912.
- Hayes, J. H and Stuart Irvine. *Isaiah the Eighth-Century Prophet: His Times and His Preaching* Nashville: Abingdon, 1987.
- House, Paul R. *Isaiah's Call in its Context* <http://faculty.gordon.edu> Accessed on Aug 12 2007
- _____, "Isaiah" *New International Bible Commentary* Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing Company, 1992
- Imasogie, Osadolor. *The Message of God for Such a Time as These*. ed. by Yusuf A. Obaje Lagos; Sibon Books, 1993

Kaiser, Otto, *Isaiah 1-1.2* Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1972

Kugel, James *The Idea of Biblical Poetry* (New Haven: Yale Publishing Company, 1981)

Leslie, Elmer A. *Isaiah*. New York: Abingdon Press, 1993

Liebreich, L. J. "The Position of Chapter Six in the Book of Isaiah," *Hebrew Union College Annual* 25 (1954) 37.

Light, G. W. *Isaiah*. Louisville, Kentucky: Geneva Press, 2001.

Lindblom, J. *Prophecy in Ancient Israel*. Oxford: Blackwell Press, 1963

Lowth, Robert, *Sacred Poetry of the Hebrews* (original 1753; reprinted Andover: Codman Press, 1829)

Motyer, J. A. *The Prophecy of Isaiah* Leicester, England: Intervarsity Press, 1993.

Napier, B. D. *Song of the Vineyard: A Guide Through the Old Testament* Philadelphia: Fortress, 1982.

Oswalt, John, "The Book of Isaiah, chapters 1-39" *New International Commentary of the Old Testament*; Grand Rapids: Williams Eerdmans, 1986.

Schmidt, W.H. *Old Testament Introduction*. New York: Walter der Gruyter, 1995.

Smith, G. A. *The Book of Isaiah Chapters 1-39* New York: Harper and Row, 1927.

Sweeney, M. A. *Isaiah 1-39 with Introduction to Prophetic Literature* Cambridge: Williams Eerdsman Publishing Company, 1996.

William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1996.

Watts, J. D. W. *Isaiah 1-33 World Biblical Commentary Vol 24* Waco, Texas: Word Books Publisher, 2003.

----"Isaiah" in Mills" *Mercer Commentary on the Bible* vol 4, Mercer University Press, 1996.

Webb, Barry *The Message of Isaiah* ed. by J. A. Motyer . Leicester, England: Intervarsity Press, 1996.

Wildberger, H. *Isaiah 1-12 A Continental Commentary*: Transl. by Thomas H. Trapp. Minneapolis: Fortress Press 1991.

Wood, L. J. *The Prophets of Israel*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Baker Book House, 2003.

Young, E. J. *The Book of Isaiah*: Vol. 1, chapters 1-18 Grand Rapids, Michigan : Eerdmans, 1965

Young, "Isaiah 1-18," 234 and Geoffrey W. Grogan *English Bible Commentary* 6; ed. F: Gaebelein; Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1986

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